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AXIONS IN DENSE QUARK MATTER

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Abstract

We investigate the effective action of the axion of Quantum Chromodynamics in an environment made of dense and cold quark matter. The axion is a hypothetical particle predicted in Quantum Chromodynamics, namely the theory of strong interactions. It was introduced as a part of a mechanism that aims at explaining the strong CP problem, that is the lack of the explicit breaking of the CP symmetry; it might have played a role in the early universe, and might still play a role in the cooling of neutron stars mergers as well as young neutron stars. We investigate the interaction of the QCD axion with dense quark matter, as the one that could be found in the core of compact stellar objects. This phase is expected to be a color superconductor, with a non-trivial ground state characterized by a nonzero quark-quark condensate that leads to interesting spontaneous symmetry breaking patterns. Potential applications of the projects involve the capture of axions in the core of the compact stellar objects (neutron stars), the formation of axion walls in the core of neutron stars, the cooling of the neutron stars mergers, and the enhancement of the axion self-coupling near the critical endpoint of the QCD phase diagram. We compute the axion mass and the axion self-coupling in the three-flavor and the two-flavor color-superconductor. Moreover, we analytically compute the topological susceptibility of the color-superconductive phases.

Introduction

Axions are hypothetical particles proposed as a solution to the strong CP (Charge-Parity) problem in quantum chromodynamics (QCD), the theory describing the strong interaction that binds quarks together inside protons and neutrons. The strong CP problem arises from the lack of observed CP violation in strong interactions, which theoretically should be present. The introduction of axions helps to explain this discrepancy. Their influence on the behavior and properties of dense quark matter, and their possible contribution can add to our understanding of compact stellar objects.

This thesis specifically pertains to the study of axions within the context of dense matter quark environments. The first chapter of this thesis furnish foundational information on the core principles that underlie the field of physics, serving as a motivational framework. Chapter 1 addresses the question, "Why do we study axions in dense quark matter?" This inquiry is intrinsically linked to the question, "Under which conditions, does dense quark matter exist?" To ensure the main goals of the thesis are easily understood, section 1.1. addresses these problems without delving into technical specifics. The second query that is answered has to do with "superconductivity."

Section 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4, examine many-particle systems that can be effectively represented using only electromagnetic interactions. It presents the foundations of the renowned BCS theory, developed in the 1950s to

explain the mechanisms of superconductivity in metals and alloys. Theoretical concepts such as "spontaneous symmetry breaking," which arise from the study of superconductivity, are also depicted in this section. Within the context of quark matter, the third theme of this thesis explores the concept of "color superconductivity" by examining its relationship with conventional superconductors. This investigation, often referred to as "condensed-matter physics of QCD," transcends a simple translation of existing theories into an alternative physical framework. The theory becomes progressively challenging due to the intricate nature of quarks, and the fundamental characteristics of QCD. Section 1.5 and 1.6 explores the Strong-CP problem in QCD and explains the axion mass and decay constant. Section 1.6 provides potential applications or environment where dense quark matter could be found and also couple with the background axion field.

In Chapter 2, it is aimed to establish a model, which provides a framework for understanding the dynamics of fermions, based on the notion of effective four-fermion interactions. The Nambu–Jona–Lasinio (NJL) model was introduced analogously to the BCS theory of superconductivity to elaborate the spontaneous chiral symmetry breaking. The model is used due to its ability to capture essential aspects of strong interaction dynamics and phase transitions in fermionic systems.

Chapter 3 focuses on the interpretation and analysis of the model in the context of Color-Flavor Locking (CFL) phase. Section 3.1, 3.2 are based on the thermodynamic potential, gap, and role of axions in the CFL phase. Section 3.3 involves computations concerning the High-Density Effective Theory (HDET). Due to asymptotic freedom in QCD (large momentum scale), at high chemical potentials μ , the only pertinent degrees of freedom are those involving interactions in the vicinity of the Fermi surface. In section 3.4 and 3.5, we analyze the axion potential and topological susceptibility respectively. We found the analytical expression for the topological susceptibility χ in the CFL phase. Eventually, we elaborated the axion mass obtained from the topological susceptibility and axion self-coupling in section 3.6.

Chapter 4 explores a modified 2SC model where one of the quarks possesses a finite mass. The influence of this mass is introduced at the primary level by adjusting the chemical potential, leading to an expression of the quark chemical potential matrix in color-flavor space. Interestingly, it was noted that the analytical expression for the topological susceptibility remains consistent across both the CFL and 2SC phases, indicating robustness in the theoretical predictions under these model variations. This underscores the model's ability to capture key aspects of phase transitions and quark matter dynamics effectively.

In Chapter 5, we state the conclusions and summarized the important results obtained in the thesis and also discussed the potential applications of dense quark matter, color superconductive phases, and axions for the further studies.

Cold and Dense Quark Matter

1.1 Phase Structure of QCD

The thermodynamic characteristics of the physical systems can be depicted through the phase diagram. In the context of quantum chromodynamics (QCD), each point in the phase diagram represents a system of quark and gluons, characterised by a temperature T and a quark chemical potential μ . On the basis of the temperature T and chemical potential μ , the QCD phase diagram can be divided into different phases. The strongly interacting matter we usually observe is actually present at the temperature below 160 MeV and quark chemical potential below 350 MeV. In this phase, QCD matter is in a confined phase and comprises the hadrons. It must be acknowledged that the study of physical theories under extreme conditions often reveals novel structures, which in turn contributes to the advancement of our understanding of the universe. It can be posited that our existing theoretical frameworks are enhanced or superseded by new theoretical frameworks. For instance, unique regions of space and time such as early universe and interiors of the compact stars can be understood by extending the knowledge of strongly interacting matter to high temperatures and/or high densities. Therefore, it can be considered that quark matter must really existed or exist in the deconfined phase known as Quark Gluon Plasma (QGP) or superconducting phase at high baryonic densities (μ).

The existence of these phases in the high-temperature/high-density regions of the QCD phase diagram can be explained by the phenomenon of asymptotic freedom [1]. This states that the interactions between quarks are weakened to an arbitrarily low extent when the energy involved increased or the distances between them are decreased. To illustrate this visually, one can begin with the bottom left corner of the phase diagram as shown in the Figure 1.1. At low temperatures and densities, quarks are found in the confined phase of hadronic matter. Heating the system of hadrons will result in its vertical movement along the temperature axis, T . This trajectory of high temperatures corresponds to the condition of the universe at very early stages after the Big Bang. For small enough μ , there is a smooth crossover from the strongly interacting hadronic matter to the QGP [2]. It is also the motivation of the collision experiments involving nuclei at ultra-relativistic high energies to recreate the conditions of early universe in the laboratory. It is important to note, however, that the crossover is not strictly a phase transition. In principle, such systems with high T and $\mu \sim 0$ are investigated using Lattice QCD [3]. The partition function of thermal QCD is analysed on a four-dimensional lattice with three spatial dimensions and one inverse temperature scale. Lattice calculations are capable of predicting the transition properties from hadrons to the quark-gluon plasma (QGP). On the other hand, as the quark density μ increases while the temperature remains low, the nuclear matter undergoes a phase transition and becomes more compressed. Following this trajectory leads to an increasingly dense quark matter could be found inside a neutron star [4]. Neutron stars are formed when gravity collapses the star and compresses the matter to ultra-high densities. The stars remain in this state for millions of years, with the temperature potentially falling below the chemical potential, which would result in the presence of a core composed of quarks in the interior. However, the existence of quark matter within neutron stars remains unconfirmed. The applications of dense matter in compact stars are further discussed in the next sections. If we continue to increase the chemical potential (μ) while keeping the temperature low, then at some unknown critical value of μ , hadronic matter becomes quark matter, and at ultra-high densities it is postulated that quarks form Cooper pairs and become color super-

conductors [5]. This region of superconducting phase or cold and dense quark matter is the subject of this thesis.

There are numerous phases of superconducting matter on the basis of symmetries for quark cooper pair condensation. In the regime of very high density (on the extreme right of phase diagram), there is proposal of the so-called Color Flavor Locking (CFL) phase. However, at intermediate densities, there are theoretical basis for the presence of Two-Flavor Color Superconductor (2SC) [6]. We will discuss these phases in detail in the section of color superconductivity. High density/low temperature phenomenology of the quark matter only takes up, down, and strange quarks to be degrees of the freedom. Our astrophysical probes such as neutron stars are not dense enough to form heavier quarks e.g. top, charm, etc.

1.2 Superconductivity

Superconductivity was discovered by Kamerlingh Onnes in 1911 [7] while experimenting with a sample of mercury to study the temperature dependence of its electrical resistance. To his surprise, Onnes found that the electrical resistivity of mercury suddenly dropped to zero when the temperature reached about 4K. This behaviour remained identical at temperatures lower than this critical temperature T_c . The transition of the sample from this state of electrical resistivity to the state in which mercury suddenly developed zero electrical resistivity indicates that the material has undergone a transformation into another state. Since zero resistivity is equivalent to infinite conductivity, this state became known as superconductivity [8] [9].

$$\sigma = \frac{1}{\rho}, \quad (1.1)$$

where ρ is electrical resistivity, and σ represents conductivity. It is natural to consider that this transition from the normal state to the superconducting state can be called a phase transition, and a parameter depends on temperature describing this distinction between the two phases can be defined as an order parameter. In other words, order parameter becomes zero above the critical temperature T_c and takes on a non-zero

Figure 1.1: Depiction of QCD Phase Diagram. The x -axis and y -axis shows quark chemical potential μ and temperatures both in MeV respectively. The curve at $\mu = 940$ MeV represents the liquid-gas phase transition. To the left of this curve, hadrons are in gaseous form while to the right in the liquid phase. Phase transition from Hadrons (confined state) to the Quark Gluon Plasma (deconfined state) state ends at a critical point at $T = 160$ MeV. There is region of neutron stars as astrophysical probe of QCD matter. At ultra-high quark densities, there is color superconducting phase of quark matter.

value below this temperature. After the discovery of superconductivity in mercury, other metals such as tin, lead, aluminium, etc. were shown to exhibit a superconducting phase at certain temperatures.

The theoretical explanation of the phenomenon of superconductivity was developed by Bardeen, Cooper and Schrieffer in 1957 [10] on the basis of Cooper pair formation. It is now known as the BCS (Bardeen, Cooper and Schrieffer) theory. The dynamics of order parameter is also constrained by development of cooper pairs in the multi-fermion system. In order to understand it, we can imagine a system of multi-electrons in a metal with

the background of lattice oscillations e.g phonons. At zero temperature, these electrons as fermionic system follows the Pauli Exclusion Principle and each of them occupy the states upto the Fermi energy $e_F = \mu$, where μ represents the chemical potential of the electron. According to the Fermi-Dirac statistics, the mean occupation number (occupation of the fermion in the given state) of the fermions for given energy e_i is given by

$$\langle n_i \rangle = \frac{1}{e^{(\epsilon_i - \mu)/k_B T} + 1}, \quad (1.2)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant. At zero temperature, above the Fermi energy e_F , all the states are empty, it can be described mathematically as

$$\langle n_i \rangle \rightarrow \begin{cases} 1 & (\epsilon_i < \mu) \\ 0 & (\epsilon_i > \mu) \end{cases}. \quad (1.3)$$

In momentum space, the occupied and unoccupied states are discriminated by Fermi surface with radius known as Fermi momentum $p_F = \hbar k_F$. It can be better understood with the help of the Fig. (1.3).

This is Fermi Surface. It separates the occupied energy states from unoccupied states. States at Fermi surface have Fermi energy $e_F = \mu$.

Figure 1.2: Two-Dimensional depiction of the Fermi Sphere.

Now in the system of free particles, Helmholtz free energy is given by

$$F = E - \mu N, \quad (1.4)$$

where N is the number of particles. At Fermi surface, free energy becomes zero, so there is no cost of adding or subtracting a new particles from the system. Consequently, if the particles near the Fermi surface exhibit a weak attraction, a BCS pair can be formed. As a bosonic entity, the pair will develop a condensate by breaking the fermion number symmetry spontaneously. It is a significant outcome that superconductivity results in the spontaneous symmetry breaking. Moreover, the superconductive ground state breaks the electromagnetic gauge symmetry, resulting in the mass of the photon and the Meissner effect [11]. The latter is characterised by the complete expulsion of magnetic fields in the region of the superconductor. The excitation energies are modified and a gap is attained between the superconducting ground state and the excited state where cooper pair are broken.

Figure 1.3: Meissner effect. Expulsion of magnetic fields by the superconductor.

1.3 Spontaneous Symmetry Breaking

In the previous section, we have discussed that spontaneous symmetry breaking is one of the outcomes of the superconductivity. In many quantum mechanical systems, spontaneous symmetry breaking is the ubiquitous phenomenon. Spontaneous Symmetry Breaking (SSB), as the name suggests, is a process in which symmetries of the system are spontaneously broken and the system ends up in the asymmetric state. We know that in physics, dynamics of the systems is governed by the Lagrangian of the system. The solution of the Lagrangian through Euler-Lagrange equations yield the equations of the motion of the system. If these particular equations of motions follow certain symmetries, but the symmetry is not satisfied by one of the lowest energy states, then we say that symmetry is spontaneously broken. Take a basic example, like a ball positioned atop a hill. The ball is in a condition of perfect symmetry. The ball can roll down the slope with ease, indicating that it is not stable. The ball eventually starts rolling down the hill in one direction on its own. Since the ball in this instance has selected a direction that has been distinguished from other directions, the symmetry is broken.

In order to study symmetries, we usually employ group theoretic formalism to better describe the structure of the system. The symmetry of the system can be described by the group G which is when gone through certain process which spontaneously breaks the symmetry remains invariant under subgroup H of the original group G . It is also important to emphasize that there is connection between phase transitions and spontaneous symmetry breaking. The order parameter which becomes non-zero below certain critical temperature in superconductor also results in spontaneous symmetry breaking as non-zero value of the order parameter enforces the symmetry group of the system to be broken. We will consider certain physical phenomenon which exhibits spontaneous symmetry breaking to illustrate the importance of this concept. The first example explains the application of condensed matter systems e.g Ferromagnetism in spontaneous symmetry breaking. In the second example, we will consider the breaking of discrete symmetry and appearance of degenerate vacua in the classical mechanical system.

1.3.1 Ferromagnetism

We can take into consideration a lattice of localized spins in which every spin vector points randomly in three dimensions. These regions of the spin-vectors are also known as domains. The system is hence macroscopically invariant under arbitrary rotations and $G = SO(3)$ is its symmetry group. It is illustrated by the Fig. (1.4). The magnetization, which represents the phase transition's order parameter in ferromagnetism, is basically zero in this non-magnetic phase.

Now if magnetic field is applied to the spin-lattice. A finite magnetization results in all microscopic spins or domains aligning in one direction at temperatures below the critical temperature T_c as depicted by the Fig. (1.5). It is evident that the system is no longer invariant to random rotations. The symmetry of the system is spontaneously broken as soon as the spin-vectors align themselves in one particular direction. This specific microscopic alignment can be represented by subgroup $H = U(1)$ which is subset of the $SU(3)$ symmetry group. In other words, symmetry group $SU(3)$ is broken down to the subgroup $U(1)$.

Figure 1.4: Depiction of random spin-vectors depicting rotational symmetry group $SO(3)$.

Figure 1.5: Vectors are aligned in one-direction due to non-zero magnetism showing $U(1)$ group structure.

1.3.2 Discrete Symmetry

We can explore the idea of spontaneous symmetry breaking by considering a classical system with a real field $\phi(t)$ with the following action

$$S = \int dt \left(\frac{1}{2} \dot{\phi}^2 - V(\phi) \right), \quad (1.5)$$

where potential $V(\phi)$ is given by

$$V(\phi) = \frac{m^2}{2} \phi^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4} \phi^4. \quad (1.6)$$

The potential given in Eq. (1.6) has the following discrete symmetry

$$\mathbb{Z}_2 : \phi \mapsto -\phi. \quad (1.7)$$

The minimum of the energy depends on the minima of the potential. However, the first term in the potential (1.6) containing m^2 can have either positive or negative sign which is crucial for describing the minima. In the case of $m^2 > 0$, the field ϕ has minimum at $\phi = 0$. This is global minima, and \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry is unbroken.

Figure 1.6: Case of global minima: $m^2 > 0$. \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry is unbroken.

On the other hand, if we consider $m^2 < 0$, we get local maximum at $\theta = 0$ and two minima and potential becomes like double-well potential. The minima exist at

$$\phi = \pm \sqrt{-\frac{m^2}{\lambda}}. \quad (1.8)$$

Figure 1.7: Case of local maxima at $\theta = 0$: $m^2 < 0$. \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry is broken.

We notice from Fig. (1.7) that there are not one unique minima but two minima. And both of them violates the discrete \mathbb{Z}_2 symmetry. Moreover, the symmetry basically transforms from one ground state to the other ground state. This is one of the most common example of spontaneous symmetry breaking and the understanding of such a simple system can be extended to real systems in quantum field theory.

1.3.3 Continuous Symmetry

Continuous symmetries are ubiquitous in the physical systems and their study point us towards rich structures in physics. We will consider the system with rotations described by group $O(N)$.

$O(N)$ group and Rotations

The group $O(N)$ is usually described as the group of $N \times N$ real orthogonal matrices in N -dimensional space. The group $O(N)$ can be further elaborated for an element $R \in O(N)$

$$R^T = R^{-1} \quad (1.9)$$

$$, R^T \cdot R = R \cdot R^T = 1. \quad (1.10)$$

The determinant of the matrix $R \in O(N)$ can be yielded as

$$\det(R) = \pm 1. \quad (1.11)$$

where $\det(R) = +1$ characterize as pure rotations in N -dimensional space, and $\det(R) = -1$ includes reflections. We will restrict our discussion to the pure rotations. We can understand $O(N)$ group by illustrating it in two dimensions ($N = 2$). In 2D space, rotations are generated only by making rotations in one plane. The rotation matrix is dependent on only one rotation angle θ

$$R = \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1.12)$$

It means that there is only one generator of rotations in $O(2)$ group. Certain physical systems can be classified by this type of group e.g magnets with continuous spin in space. Similarly, in three $O(3)$ and four

dimensions $O(4)$, we find that there are 3 (three independent rotation planes) and 6 (six independent rotation planes) generators respectively. The physical application of $O(3)$ models is also about magnet known as Heisenberg model and $O(4)$ is linear- σ model which we will discuss specifically. The number of generators can be generalized and be found for N -dimensions by using following formula

$$\text{No of Generators} = \frac{N(N-1)}{2}, \quad (1.13)$$

After knowing briefly about the group $O(N)$, we can discuss the models related to the group. Consider N -dimensional real vector with scalar fields

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = (\phi^1(\mathbf{x}), \phi^2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, \phi^N(\mathbf{x})), \quad (1.14)$$

The action of R on the field ϕ is given by

$$(R \cdot \phi)_k = R_{kl}\phi_l, \quad (1.15)$$

where $k, l = 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots, N$. We will constrain ourselves to $N = 4$ and explain linear- σ model because it is nearest effective model to the QCD.

Linear- σ Model

We consider a theory of four-dimensional real field

$$\phi(\mathbf{x}) = (\phi^1(\mathbf{x}), \phi^2(\mathbf{x}), \phi^3(\mathbf{x}), \phi^4(\mathbf{x})) \equiv \phi^k(\mathbf{x}), \quad (1.16)$$

with Lagrangian density that is invariant under $O(4)$ rotations: $\phi_a(\mathbf{x}) \rightarrow R_a^b \phi_b(\mathbf{x})$

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \phi^k)^2 - \frac{m^2}{2} (\phi^k)^2 - \frac{\lambda}{4} [(\phi^k)^2]^2, \quad (1.17)$$

Now if we consider the second term in the Lagrangian, and use $m^2 \equiv -\mu^2 < 0$ with ϕ being constant. We get the Lagrangian and potential energy as

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \phi^k)^2 + \frac{\mu^2}{2} (\phi^k)^2 - \frac{\lambda}{4} [(\phi^k)^2]^2. \quad (1.18)$$

$$V(\phi) = -\frac{\mu^2}{2} (\phi^k)^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4} \left[(\phi^k)^2 \right]^2. \quad (1.19)$$

It can be demonstrated that an infinite set of degenerate minima (ground states) exists and they make up an hypersphere.

$$(\phi_0^k)^2 = \frac{\mu^2}{\lambda}. \quad (1.20)$$

Now, we choose one direction among these ground states and call it vacuum in the following way

$$\phi_0 = (0, 0, 0, v), \quad v = \frac{\mu}{\sqrt{\lambda}}. \quad (1.21)$$

We observe that vacuum is changed by the $O(4)$ transformation and no longer remains invariant under $O(4)$ group: $R\phi_0 \neq \phi_0$. In other words, the ground state breaks the $O(4)$ symmetry though the Lagrangian remains invariant. In order to obtain novel physics from such a theory, we build the fluctuations on the top of ground state and analyze it. We write the fluctuations as

$$\phi^k(x) = (\pi^1(x), \pi^2(x), \pi^3(x), v + \sigma(x)), \quad (1.22)$$

where π^i are the pion modes and σ is sigma mode. Using this redefinition of the field in terms of these modes, we rewrite the Lagrangian from Eq. (1.17).

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \pi^i)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu \sigma)^2 - \frac{(2\mu^2)}{2} \sigma^2 - V(\sigma, \pi), \quad (1.23)$$

and potential $V(\sigma, \pi)$ takes the form

$$V(\sigma, \pi) = \sqrt{\lambda} \mu \sigma^3 + \sqrt{\lambda} \mu (\pi^i)^2 \sigma + \frac{\lambda}{4} \sigma^4 + \frac{\lambda}{2} (\pi^i)^2 \sigma^2 + \frac{\lambda}{4} \left[(\pi^i)^2 \right]^2. \quad (1.24)$$

We can observe that the σ field becomes massive due to the term $\mu^2 = M^2/2$ which contains mass. Also, we see that Lagrangian depends on three π^i fields, which are basically massless. Similarly, we also see that

potential becomes only $O(3)$ invariant because of the dependence on $(\pi^i)^2$. In summary, we started with four-dimensional field theory which had infinite degenerate minima, we chosen one ground state and build fluctuations on the top of it. Eventually we obtain a theory which has three massless fields and one massive field along with spontaneously breaking down of symmetry from $O(4)$ to $O(3)$. The noteworthy outcome of spontaneous breaking from $O(4)$ to $O(3)$ resulted in the emergence of three massless bosons, which has significant implications in the context of the novel physical structure. The generation of massless bosons for the spontaneous breaking of global continuous symmetries is known as the Goldstone theorem. In this very example of $O(4)$ model, it can be stated as

$$\delta = \text{No of generators in } O(4) - \text{No of generators in } O(3), \quad (1.25)$$

$$\delta = 6 - 3 = 3. \quad (1.26)$$

Therefore, it is no mere coincidence that difference between generators of $O(4)$ and $O(3)$ is three which is the same number of massless bosons generated in the spontaneous breaking of symmetry. But it is consequence of the Goldstone theorem.

1.4 Color Superconductivity

We came to know that arbitrarily weak attraction between electrons in condensed matter systems is reason behind metal becoming a superconductor. Although, in such systems with presence of dominant Coulomb repulsion, it is hard to find the mechanisms behind the attractive channels. In conventional superconductors, these cooper pairs are formed with equal and opposite momentum due to the attractive mediation of the phonons and their interaction with electrons.

A similar conclusion can be drawn if we consider the replacement of the Fermi sea of electrons by quarks interacting via strong nuclear forces. In this scenario, the application of BCS theory remains intact. However, the quark-quark interaction has two color channels, one is the color-symmetric $\mathbf{6}$ channel and the other is the anti-symmetric $\bar{\mathbf{3}}$ channel. The

interaction is attractive in the anti-symmetric $\bar{3}$ channel [12]. One of the realization of the attractive channel is one-gluon exchange [13]. Therefore, the attractive interaction is naturally present in the theory of QCD. As a consequence, the Cooper instability can be realised and quarks can also be condensed to form quark-Cooper pairs [14]. This phenomenon of pairing in dense quark matter is known as color superconductivity. It means that two quarks which form a pair are related by a correlation function which can be measured in the form of particle-particle expectation value. When the particle-particle expectation value is non-zero, there will be formation of pairs. Mathematically it can be written as

$$\langle \psi_{ia}^\alpha \psi_{jb}^\beta \rangle = \Delta \neq 0, \quad (1.27)$$

where a, b are spin indices, $\alpha, \beta \in (\text{red, green, blue})$ color indices, and $i, j \in (\text{up, down, strange})$ are color indices. And Δ is also called as gap. In color superconductivity, the local color symmetry $SU(3)_c$ is spontaneously broken as quarks cannot be color-singlets, this leads to the masses of the gluons similar to the generation of mass of photon in QED (Quantum Electrodynamics) superconductivity [15]. Similar to superconductivity, color superconductors also acquire the gap [13] in the energy spectrum,

$$\epsilon_k = \sqrt{(E_{\mathbf{k}} - \mu)^2 + \Delta^2}, \quad (1.28)$$

E_k is the dispersion of a particle with mass m : $E(k) = \sqrt{\vec{k}^2 + m^2}$. The gap in the energy can affect the thermodynamic and transport properties of the quark matter. It means that if there is presence of quark matter inside the interior of neutron stars, then empirical observations from pulsars such as mechanism behind the rotational period, cooling down, and sudden glitches in the rotational period of neutron stars. In comparison to electrons, quarks have color charge, different flavors, and electric charge which allows for different phases of color superconductive structures. On the basis of quantum numbers of quarks, there are different pairing patterns that can be followed and each of them results in different phases with different symmetry breaking and hence rich physical structure. According to number of quark flavors N_f , we will discuss most important phases in the color superconductivity.

1.4.1 Two and Three Flavor Color Superconductor

The simplest case is of considering two light quark flavors, $N_f = 2$, which are up and down quarks. The strange quark can be ignored at the intermediate quark chemical potential. This phase of two-flavors participating in the pairing is also known as 2SC. The colors which participate in the pairing are red and green, and the blue quarks remain unpaired. The gauge structure of the dynamical equations remains invariant, regardless of the choice of choosing blue quarks as to be unpaired. The Cooper pairs in the 2SC phase are formed in the color anti-triplet, flavor singlet, and spin singlet channels. These channels are anti-symmetric with respect to the exchange of quantum numbers of individual quarks, thus following the Pauli exclusion principle, the requirement for the complete wavefunction to be anti-symmetric. The 2SC condensate can be written as

$$\langle \psi_{i\alpha} \psi_{j\beta} \rangle = \Delta \varepsilon_{ij} \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta 3}, \quad (1.29)$$

where i, j represents the flavor indices, and α, β are color indices. As it is stated earlier that superconducting states breaks the symmetries due to the Anderson-Higgs mechanism. Thus, the symmetry group breaking pattern in 2SC is following

$$SU(3)_c \times SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \times U(1)_Q \times U(1)_B, \quad (1.30)$$

$$\longrightarrow SU(2)_c \times SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R \times U(1)_{\tilde{Q}} \times U(1)_{\tilde{B}}. \quad (1.31)$$

where $SU(3)_c$ and $U(1)_Q$ are the color and electromagnetic gauge groups, $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ is the chiral symmetry group which can also be written as flavor group $SU(2)_F = SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$, and $U(1)_B$ is the baryon number group. The color gauge group $SU(3)_c$ is broken down to the $SU(2)_c$ and 5 of the gluons acquire Meissner mass. The unbroken $SU(2)_{rg}$ symmetry is associated with remaining three gluons. The red-green quarks acquire gaps in the energy gap, whereas blue quarks remain unpaired. The electromagnetic symmetry $U(1)_Q$ is broken but it does not mean that 2SC phase is also electromagnetic superconductor [16]. However, it is replaced by modified group $U(1)_{\tilde{Q}}$ which is the linear combination of the color and electromagnetic gauge group. On a similar note, $U(1)_B$ is replaced by $U(1)_{\tilde{B}}$ as linear combination of T_8 color generator. The

transformations are given by

$$\tilde{Q} = Q - \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}}T_8, \quad (1.32)$$

$$\tilde{B} = B - \frac{2}{\sqrt{3}}T_8. \quad (1.33)$$

The chiral symmetry group $SU(2)_L \times SU(2)_R$ remains intact. There are no global symmetries which are broken in the 2SC case. This implies that there is no order parameter between the 2SC phase and the quark-gluon plasma, and thus, there is no phase transition between the two phases of quark matter. Our analysis can be expanded to encompass high-density scenarios in which strange quarks also become part of the dynamics. In a manner analogous to the 2SC case, the total wavefunction is anti-symmetric. However, in the three-quark phase, the flavor channel is anti-symmetric anti-triplet. Moreover, condensate of three-flavors color superconductor with appropriate anti-symmetric properties can be written as

$$\langle \psi_{i\alpha} \psi_{j\beta} \rangle = \Delta \sum_{I=1}^3 \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta I} \varepsilon_{ijI}, \quad (1.34)$$

And as we know from the properties of Levi-Civita tensor that it can be re-written in the form of δ functions, so we write

$$\sum_{I=1}^3 \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta I} \varepsilon_{ijI} = \delta_{\alpha i} \delta_{\beta j} - \delta_{\alpha j} \delta_{\beta i}, \quad (1.35)$$

It is evident from the Eq. (1.35) that color and flavor indices are mixed in the δ function. This means that both color and flavor of the quarks are locked together. This is the reason is that this phase is also known as Color-Flavor Locking (CFL) phase. Similarly, we can also look at the symmetry breaking pattern in the case of CFL phase as

$$SU(3)_c \times SU(3)_L \times SU(3)_R \times U(1)_Q \times U(1)_B, \quad (1.36)$$

$$\longrightarrow SU(3)_{c+L+R} \times U(1)_{\tilde{Q}} \times \mathbb{Z}_2. \quad (1.37)$$

The color gauge group $SU(3)_c$ is broken altogether. All the eighth gluons acquire Meissner mass through symmetric breaking mechanism. The

spectrum of all three quarks e.g red, green, and blue is gapped in this case. One of the interesting feature of this phase is that chiral symmetries are also broken. The procedure of this chiral symmetry breaking is quite different than the formation of the $\langle \bar{\psi}\psi \rangle$ in vacuum which mixes the left-handed components with right-handed components. In this instance, the left-handed components of the quarks pair with each other, while the right-handed components pair with themselves. The representation $SU(3)_{c+L+R}$ indicates that both color and flavor groups are locked together. Any rotation in the color group is accompanied by a simultaneous rotation in the flavor group, and vice versa.

1.5 Strong CP Problem and QCD Axion

One of the foundational pillars of the modern quantum field theory is quantum chromodynamics (QCD), which elucidates the interactions between quarks mediated by gluons, thereby providing an explanation for the observed phenomena. QCD is characterized by the asymptotic freedom, color confinement, and chiral symmetry breaking. Quantum chromodynamics is represented by non-abelian $SU(3)$ color group, which allows the terms of the form in the QCD Lagrangian density

$$\mathcal{L}_\theta \propto \theta F \cdot \tilde{F}, \quad (1.38)$$

The parameter θ represents the real quantity, F denotes the field strength tensor, and \tilde{F} is the dual of F . In the early stages of the development of the theory of quantum chromodynamics (QCD), a perplexing issue emerged regarding the $U(1)_A$ anomaly [17] [18]. While initially appearing to be a symmetry at the theoretical level, it was later discovered to be broken in the real world. The solution to this problem introduced the term (1.38) into the Lagrangian density of QCD. The introduction of this term, as a consequence of non-trivial vacuum structure of QCD [19], resulted in the breakdown of internal symmetries present in QFT, charge conjugation and parity (CP), and the CP symmetry is no longer preserved in the QCD Lagrangian. In charge conjugation, particles are replaced with their respective anti-particles, whereas parity transformation is achieved through an inversion of spatial coordinates. This latter transformation

is sometimes referred to as mirror symmetry. Consequently, the neutron acquires an electric dipole moment due to the breakdown of CP symmetry. The current best estimate on the limit of the neutron electric dipole moment (nEDM) [20] is found to be

$$|d_n| < 1.8 \times 10^{-26} \text{e.cm.} \quad (1.39)$$

Nevertheless, the current experimental constraints on the dipole moment necessitate that the θ -angle be less than 10^{-11} . The angle θ can take any value between 0 and 2π . The necessity of fine-tuning the value of θ to such a small magnitude or no empirical justification of presence of electric dipole moment of neutron raises the issue of the Strong-CP problem in QCD [21]. It has been suggested that Strong-CP problem can be resolved by considering pseudo-scalar field, a , which couples to the gluon field strength tensors, we get

$$\mathcal{L}_a = \frac{a}{f_a} F \cdot \tilde{F}, \quad (1.40)$$

where f_a is basically the mass scale called as decay constant of a field. The value of PQ scale, f_a are dependent on the beyond standard model theories. By adding the Eq. (1.38) in (1.40), we write the complete CP-violating part of the QCD Lagrangian

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{CP-V}} = \theta F \cdot \tilde{F} + \frac{a}{f_a} F \cdot \tilde{F}. \quad (1.41)$$

The coupling of a to the gluon fields will develop the potential for itself, resulting in an expectation of $\langle \theta + a/f_a \rangle = 0$, which specifies that the potential contains a minimum. As a consequence of a natural relaxation of the a potential, the effective θ angle turns out to be zero in the QCD vacuum, potentially solving the strong CP problem. This is also known as Peccei and Quinn mechanism [22] [23]. They posed that Standard Model (SM) has another global $U(1)_{\text{PQ}}$ chiral symmetry which is spontaneously broken down. Wilczek [24] and Weinberg [25] identified the pseudo-Nambu Goldstone boson related to the field, and Wilczek called it axion.

1.5.1 Axion mass and decay constant

The axion mass can be determined by mixing the axion with the neutral pion, as they share the same quantum numbers. The interactions between

the axion and the neutral pion allow the pion's mass to contribute a small mass to the axion. This effect is possible only because of their identical quantum numbers, leading to the following relation for the axion mass [26]:

$$m_a f_a \approx m_\pi f_\pi, \quad (1.42)$$

By utilizing the experimental measurements of pion mass and f_π , where f_π is decay constant of pions in weak interactions, we can determine the axion mass [27]

$$m_a = (5.70 \pm 0.007) \mu eV \left(\frac{10^{12} \text{ GeV}}{f_a} \right). \quad (1.43)$$

We see that axion mass depends on the f_a which in essence is model-dependent parameter. Already, there are quite stringent experimental constraints on the axion's existence [8]. Models where the f_a is of the order of the electroweak scale are ruled out due to the non-observation of an axion in decay experiments. Nonetheless, these limitations can consistently be circumvented by elevating the PQ scale [9, 10], or conversely, decreasing the mass of the axion, thereby minimizing the axion's couplings with identifiable particles. Therefore, in order to constrain the mass and relevant mass scale of the axions we have to consider the regions of astrophysical interest as given by Fig. (1.8). The upper bound on the axion mass can be established by the supernova SN1987A [28]. This can be done by studying relationship between nuclear matter coupling g_{aNN} to the axions. In the radiation emission from the supernova explosion, axions can be emitted from the collapsing core of the dying star. Supernovae also emit neutrinos, which serve as a recognized cooling pathway. If axions are also created, the supernova will cool faster and have less time to emit neutrinos, resulting in a decreased neutrino flux. The neutrinos produced in SN 1987A were detected in neutrino detectors on Earth.

Moreover, axions were also to be found as interesting candidates of the cold dark matter contributing to the significant portion of the matter in the universe. At cosmological scales, the generation of axions is related to the misalignment mechanism in the early universe. There is also one

interesting quantity related to the mass of axion, and is of core interest of this thesis is topological susceptibility which can be defined as

$$\chi = m_a^2 f_a^2. \quad (1.44)$$

Figure 1.8: Relevant model-dependent scales of axion mass m_a and decay constant f_a [29].

1.6 Applications to Compact Stars

It is natural to consider experimental implications of our theoretical ideas which is to ask that where in nature we can find the empirical probes for dense quark matter and ultimately superconducting quark matter phases. The only place nature has to offer are the compact stars mainly neutron stars. Neutron stars results in a supernova explosion. These stellar objects are thought to have radii of about 10 km and masses of about $1.4M_{Sun}$.

Although we are unaware of the value in the core due to uncertainties regarding the equation of state, the density varies from around nuclear density at the surface to larger values further in. The first observational evidence of the neutron stars came in 1960's. They are dubbed as neutron stars because, at high densities, a phenomena known as "neutron drip" occurs, in which neutrons begin to reside independently in equilibrium with nuclei and electrons. As the star's density of nuclear matter approaches higher chemical potential as depicted in QCD phase diagram, nuclei are no longer present, and a phase of neutrons, protons, and electrons is preferred. At higher densities, a phase including muons, and hyperons is anticipated to be the preferred state. This means that the up and down quarks begin to form new hadrons, and the heavier strange quarks could also be participating. The density could increase far higher than the density which sustains the hadrons, and the star's interior is believed to contain quark matter. We have given the description that how compact stars like neutron stars can form the dense quark matter. However, the "cold" part of the cold and dense quark matter emerges as during the evolution of neutron stars from high temperatures to eventual cool down. The temperature of neutron star at the start of its formation is estimated to be 10^{11} K which after evolution of million years cools down to 10^5 K. The dominant mechanism behind this cooling down of the temperature is proposed as the emission of the neutrinos.

There are also two observational facts coming from the observations of pulsars. One is the rotational spin down of the pulsar and the other is sudden spin-ups known as glitches. The population of pulsars evolving in consequence of rotational spin down dynamics are plotted in the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram in Fig. (1.9). The picture of the neutron stars which develops because of theoretical explorations like nuclear equation of state and experimental facts such as observed spin-down and glitches is given by Fig. (1.10). The crust of neutron stars contain neutron-rich nuclei and electrons extended to a proportion of total radius of 10 km. In this region, there might exist superfluid neutrons which are considered as one of the reasons of the observed glitches in the neutron stars. The rotation of the star generates an array of vortex lines, which expand as the star spins down. The sudden jumps in rotation frequency can be attributed to the

fact that the vortex lines are pinned to the crust of the star.

Figure 1.9: We plot the $P - \dot{P}$ diagram for about 2000 known pulsars listed in the ATNF catalogue. The lines of constant τ are in red, and the lines of constant B are in blue. Pulsars part of a binary system are not plotted.

Inside the interior, the neutron, protons, electrons, and muons co-exist together where protons forming a superconductor. Further inside the core, there is possibility of existence of strange quark matter and color-

superconducting phases such as 2SC and CFL which we discussed in the previous sections. The 2SC phases can exist at intermediate densities where only up and down quark make BCS pair while CFL phases at higher densities where strange quark also take part in making cooper pairs.

Figure 1.10: Proposed phases of Neutron Stars [30].

Besides presence of the superconducting phases of quark matter inside the interior of the neutron stars, the axions can also be present deep inside these astrophysical objects. These axions can potentially interact with the quark matter and motivates the study of axions in dense quark matter.

The axions from these compact objects can be released by primakov effect (converting of an axion into a photon) as a result of high magnetic fields and ejected into the space and be detected in the narrow radio lines. The axions could also be another mechanism of cooling down of neutron stars besides neutrino emissions.

Model

To develop the theoretical model of axion interaction with dense quark matter, we should naturally begin with the first principle QCD e.g lattice QCD. Lattice QCD calculations, despite their success to explain the dynamics of phase diagram of QCD at $\mu \neq 0$, fails to provide adequate understanding of the phase diagram due to the sign-problem. The presence of the sign problem undermines the effectiveness of importance sampling at $\mu \neq 0$, rendering the generation of a gauge ensemble unfeasible [31]. In other words, the sign problem become apparent as soon as one integrates the fermions and writes down the partion function in the form of guage fields. For instance, integration of each fermion generates a factor of

$$\det(\mathcal{D} + m + \mu\gamma_0), \quad (2.1)$$

where $\mu\gamma_0$ factor is natural to the system when $\mu \neq 0$. And \mathcal{D} is the Dirac operator. This Dirac operator \mathcal{D} follows the hermiticity related to the γ_5

$$\gamma_5 \mathcal{D} \gamma_5 = \mathcal{D}^\dagger, \quad (2.2)$$

Therefore, applying the γ_5 operators, we obtain

$$\gamma_5(\mathcal{D} + m + \mu\gamma_0)\gamma_5 = \mathcal{D}^\dagger + m - \mu\gamma_0, \quad (2.3)$$

$$= (\mathcal{D} + m - \mu^*\gamma_0)^\dagger. \quad (2.4)$$

Now, if we consider the determinant on the both sides, we get

$$\det(\mathcal{D} + m + \mu\gamma_0) = \det^*(\mathcal{D} + m - \mu^*\gamma_0), \quad (2.5)$$

From Eq. (2.5), the determinant is only bound to be real if μ is either zero or imaginary. Therefore, the sampling of finite chemical potential μ ensemble becomes significant issue [32] and we cannot consider lattice QCD for the high density quark matter. A potential avenue for further exploration is the application of perturbative QCD. However, it is similarly challenging to conduct reliable calculations within the framework of improved-pQCD, particularly with regards to the quark chemical potential values that are of phenomenological interest.

The issue with lattice QCD and improved-QCD at high quark chemical potential provides a rationale for examining the interaction of axions in dense quark matter with a QCD-like model that defines the dynamics of phase transitions and encapsulates the axions. The models that possess the same symmetries of QCD are postulated to be sufficient for encompassing the approximate structure of the QCD phases at large density. One of such most widely used models is the Nambu–Jona–Lasinio (NJL) model, which provides a framework for understanding the dynamics of fermions, based on the notion of effective four-fermion interactions. We will have a brief look on NJL model in the following section.

2.1 Nambu-Jona Lasino Model

The Nambu-Jona-Lasinio (NJL) model was developed to elucidate the mechanism underlying spontaneous chiral symmetry breaking in the vacuum, a phenomenon analogous to the BCS mechanism underlying superconductivity. The model was initially presented at a time when both QCD and quarks were yet to be established as fundamental concepts in physics. Its original form was designed for modelling interactions among nucleons, with confinement not yet a concern. Prior to the development of quantum chromodynamics (QCD), there were evidence of the presence of a approximately preserved axial vector current, which can be interpreted as chiral symmetry. Because (approximate) chiral symmetry implies the absence of mass for fermions at the Lagrangian level, the goal was to find a mechanism that could account for the observed nucleon mass while maintaining the symmetry. Nambu and Jona-Lasinio proposed that the

mass gap in the Dirac spectrum of the nucleon might be formed in a way similar to the energy gap of a superconductor in BCS theory, which had been developed a few years previously. Following the discovery of QCD, the NJL model was reinterpreted as a schematic quark model. At that point, the lack of confinement posed a substantial barrier to the model's applicability. Nonetheless, there are plenty of situations in which chiral symmetry is a critical element of QCD, with confinement playing a secondary role. The most illustrative example is the Goldstone nature of the pion. In this aspect, the NJL model has an obvious edge over the MIT bag model, which fails to account for the small pion mass. Eventually, model also became relevant for studying the superconducting phases of dense quark matter. Nambu-Jona and Lasino proposed the Lagrangian with nucleon field ψ and four vertex fermion interaction term in the following manner

$$\mathcal{L} = \bar{\psi}(i\not{\partial} - m)\psi + G \left\{ (\bar{\psi}\psi)^2 + (\bar{\psi}i\gamma_5\vec{\tau}\psi)^2 \right\}, \quad (2.6)$$

In this equation, m represents the nucleon's low bare mass, τ is isospin matrix, and G is a coupling constant with dimensions. As we stated earlier that after the discovery of QCD and quarks, NJL models were reinterpreted due to instrumental role in different scenarios, the nucleon field ψ could also be considered to take a role of quark field with two degrees of freedom in flavor space and three in color space. However, there are numerous alternative chirally symmetric interaction terms that can be presented [33]. Modern approaches considers local 4-point interactions between quarks in a two-flavor system to be separate from instanton-induced interactions. In this situation, the interaction Lagrangian should take the following form:

$$\mathcal{L}_{int} = G \left\{ (\bar{q}q)^2 - (\bar{q}\vec{\tau}q)^2 - (\bar{q}i\gamma_5q)^2 + (\bar{q}i\gamma_5\vec{\tau}q)^2 \right\}. \quad (2.7)$$

Nambu and Jona-Lasinio approximated the quark's self-energy produced by the interaction term using the Hatree or Hartree-Fock approximation [34].

$$M = m + 2iG \int \frac{d^4p}{(2\pi)^4} \text{Tr}S(p), \quad (2.8)$$

where dressed quark propagator $S(p)$ is given by

$$S(p) = (\not{p} - M + i\epsilon). \quad (2.9)$$

Now, considering the trace over Dirac, flavor and color spaces, we get

$$M = m + 8iGN_fN_c \int \frac{d^4p}{(2\pi)^4} \frac{M}{p^2 - M^2 + i\epsilon}. \quad (2.10)$$

Here N_f and N_c are the numbers of flavors and colors, respectively. Mass M is the constituent quark mass. The Eq. (2.10) is also known as the gap equation. In the case of two-flavors and three colors, and strong coupling G , the energy gap becomes $\Delta E = 2M$. The constituent mass M is related to the quark condensate which is given by

$$\langle \bar{q}q \rangle = -i \int \frac{d^4p}{(2\pi)^4} \text{Tr}S(p), \quad (2.11)$$

In our case due to the equation (2.10), it becomes

$$\langle \bar{q}q \rangle = -\frac{M - m}{2G}. \quad (2.12)$$

The value of the chiral condensate can be obtained by the operator product expansion (OPE)

$$\langle \bar{q}q \rangle \approx (-0.23 \text{ GeV})^3. \quad (2.13)$$

The non-zero chiral condensate effectively give large masses (constituent) to the quarks even though they are assumed to be massless at QCD Lagrangian. The constituent mass M of a quark is of order of 300 – 400 MeV. The finite value of chiral condensate results in the spontaneous breaking of chiral symmetry. One of the most significant consequences of this is the emergence of light pseudo-scalar mesons, or pions, within the QCD spectrum. Through pions, we can calculate the values of the up and down quark masses

$$m_\pi^2 = -\frac{m_u + m_d}{F_\pi^2} \langle \bar{q}q \rangle. \quad (2.14)$$

By using values of $F_{pi} = 193\text{MeV}$ and $m_\pi = 136\text{MeV}$ [35].

$$m_u + m_d \approx 13 \text{ MeV}. \quad (2.15)$$

These values are small in comparison to the constituent mass M . The explicit breaking of the chiral symmetry in QCD is a relatively soft phenomenon.

2.2 Lagrangian Density

Our suggestion is that we start with the following Lagrangian density:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = g_1(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q)(\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + g_2(q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q)(\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T). \quad (2.16)$$

In the Lagrangian density (2.16), q^T is transposed field operator, $\bar{q} = q^\dagger \gamma^0$ operator creates a quark or annihilates an anti-quark, and charge conjugation matrix $C = -i \gamma_2 \gamma_0$, satisfying $C^2 = C^\dagger C = -1$. In addition, we can utilize compact notation for simplicity, which omits the colour and flavour indices associated with the fields and the Levi-Civita symbols in each bilinear.

$$q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q = q_{\alpha i}^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon_{\alpha \beta I} \epsilon_{ij I} q_{\beta j}. \quad (2.17)$$

where i, j depicts the flavor indices and α, β represents the color indices. It is important to note that $\epsilon_{\alpha \beta I} \epsilon_{ij I}$ are Levi-Civita tensors implying anti-symmetry in the context of CFL (color-flavor locking) phase. This type of Lagrangian density has been employed in the spirit of the previous works in the field of color superconductivity. In those works, it is assumed that $g_1 = g_2$, thereby preserving the $U(1)_A$ symmetry at the Lagrangian level. However, in our study, we start with the assumption that $g_1 \neq g_2$, intentionally breaking the $U(1)_A$ symmetry in the Lagrangian to emulating the effects of instanton-mediated interactions. To separate the $U(1)_A$ symmetry violating term from the $U(1)_A$ invariant term, we can use (2.16), while adding and subtracting the terms: $g_2(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q)(\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T)$ and $g_1(q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q)(\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T)$, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = & \frac{(g_1 + g_2)}{2} \left[(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + (q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) \right] \\ & + \frac{(g_1 - g_2)}{2} \left[(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) - (q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

The second line of (2.18) breaks the $U(1)_A$ symmetry. The equation (2.18) can be further simplified by writing down the projection operators, $q = (\mathcal{P}_L + \mathcal{P}_R)q$:

$$\mathcal{P}_R = \frac{1 + \gamma_5}{2}, \quad \mathcal{P}_L = \frac{1 - \gamma_5}{2}, \quad (2.19)$$

By using the (2.19), the second line of the equation (2.18) can be rewritten in the following manner

$$(g_1 - g_2) \left[(q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + (q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) \right], \quad (2.20)$$

Here, we define $G_D = (g_1 + g_2)/2$, $\zeta G_D = (g_1 - g_2)$. We have also used $\gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L q = -\mathcal{P}_L q = -q_L$ and $\gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R q = \mathcal{P}_R q = q_R$. Eventually, we can write the Lagrangian density [36] as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = & G_D \left[(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + (q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) \right] \\ & + \zeta G_D (q^T C \mathcal{P}_L \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} \mathcal{P}_L C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + \zeta G_D (q^T C \mathcal{P}_R \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} \mathcal{P}_R C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T). \end{aligned}$$

Then, we couple the $U_A(1)$ symmetry-breaking term to the axion-background field because this term comes from the one instanton exchange. The term basically contains non-zero $F \cdot \tilde{F}$ which violates the CP-symmetry as discussed before.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = & G_D \left[(q^T C i \gamma_5 \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + (q^T C \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) \right] \\ & + \zeta G_D e^{ia/f_a} (q^T C \mathcal{P}_L \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} \mathcal{P}_L C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T) + \zeta G_D e^{-ia/f_a} (q^T C \mathcal{P}_R \epsilon \epsilon q) (\bar{q} \mathcal{P}_R C \epsilon \epsilon \bar{q}^T). \end{aligned} \quad (2.21)$$

The interactive Lagrangian is completely specified by the equation (2.21). The first line which preserves the $U(1)_A$ symmetry depicts the quark-quark interaction due to the one-gluon exchange. However, the second

line which violates the $U(1)_A$ is related to the one-instanton exchange. It is worth noting that not all references to color superconductivity include both terms in the (2.21); in the cases where they do, they usually neglect the second term when taking the mean-field approximation. This is due to the fact that they assume only condensation in the scalar channel, while the second line depends on condensation in the pseudo-scalar channel. The model is studied under the mean-field approximation. We are introducing quark condensates to apply the mean-field approximation in the following way

$$\langle q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L \varepsilon \varepsilon q \rangle = -h_L, \quad (2.22)$$

$$\langle \bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T \rangle = h_R^*, \quad (2.23)$$

$$\langle q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R \varepsilon \varepsilon q \rangle = h_R, \quad (2.24)$$

$$\langle \bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T \rangle = -h_L^*. \quad (2.25)$$

In expanded notation with the indices, it can be understood as

$$\langle q_{\alpha i}^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L \varepsilon_{\alpha \beta I} \varepsilon_{ij I} q_{\beta j} \rangle = -h_L, \quad \langle q_{\alpha i}^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R \varepsilon_{\alpha \beta I} \varepsilon_{ij I} q_{\beta j} \rangle = h_R, \quad (2.26)$$

And the combinations of quark condensates can be defined as

$$\langle q^T C i \gamma_5 \varepsilon \varepsilon q \rangle = h_R - h_L, \quad (2.27)$$

$$\langle \bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T \rangle = h_R^* - h_L^*, \quad (2.28)$$

Employing these equations with premise that $h_L^* = h_L$ and $h_R^* = h_R$, we can rewrite the Lagrangian density in the mean-field approximation

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = & G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon \left[(h_R - h_L) (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) + (h_R^* - h_L^*) (q^T C i \gamma_5 \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] - G_D (h_R - h_L) (h_R^* - h_L^*) \\ & - G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon \left[(h_R + h_L) (\bar{q} i C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) - (h_R^* + h_L^*) (q^T C \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] - G_D (h_R + h_L) (h_R^* + h_L^*) \\ & + \zeta G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon e^{i \frac{\theta}{f_a}} \left[-h_L (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) + h_R^* (q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] + \zeta G_D e^{i \frac{\theta}{f_a}} h_L h_R^* \\ & + \zeta G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon e^{-i \frac{\theta}{f_a}} \left[h_R (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R C \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) - h_L^* (q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] + \zeta G_D e^{-i \frac{\theta}{f_a}} h_L^* h_R. \quad (2.29) \end{aligned}$$

The assumption of real h_L and h_R leads to the simplified interaction lagrangian

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = & G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon (h_R - h_L) \left[(\bar{q} i \gamma_5 C \varepsilon \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) + (q^T C i \gamma_5 \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] - G_D (h_R - h_L)^2 \\
& - G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon \left[(h_R + h_L) (\bar{q} i C \varepsilon \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) - (h_R + h_L) (q^T C \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] - G_D (h_R + h_L)^2 \\
& + \zeta G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon e^{i \frac{a}{f_a}} \left[-h_L (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L C \varepsilon \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) + h_R (q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_L \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] + \zeta G_D e^{i \frac{a}{f_a}} h_L h_R \\
& + \zeta G_D \varepsilon \varepsilon e^{-i \frac{a}{f_a}} \left[h_R (\bar{q} i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R C \varepsilon \varepsilon \bar{q}^T) - h_L (q^T C i \gamma_5 \mathcal{P}_R \varepsilon \varepsilon q) \right] + \zeta G_D e^{-i \frac{a}{f_a}} h_L h_R.
\end{aligned} \tag{2.30}$$

Note that $\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{int}}^\dagger$.

In our analysis, we introduce the Nambu-Gorkov bi-spinors, which provide a convenient framework for describing the pairing of quarks in a color superconducting phase. These bi-spinors combine quark and anti-quark degrees of freedom into a single two-component object, facilitating the treatment of quark pairs that form color-condensed states. In particular, the Nambu-Gorkov bi-spinor can be defined as:

$$\Psi = \begin{pmatrix} q \\ C \bar{q}^T \end{pmatrix}, \quad \bar{\Psi} = (\bar{q}, q^T C). \tag{2.31}$$

By using Nambu-Gorkov formalism, we then can rewrite the interaction lagrangian density as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \mathcal{V} + \bar{\Psi} \Delta \Psi, \tag{2.32}$$

where

$$\mathcal{V} = -2G_D (h_R^2 + h_L^2) + 2\zeta G_D h_L h_R \cos\left(\frac{a}{f_a}\right), \tag{2.33}$$

and

$$\Delta = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Phi^- \\ \Phi^+ & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \tag{2.34}$$

with

$$\Phi^- = G_D \left[2h_R \mathcal{P}_L - 2h_L \mathcal{P}_R - e^{ia/f_a} h_L \zeta \mathcal{P}_L + e^{-ia/f_a} h_R \zeta \mathcal{P}_R \right] i\gamma_5 \varepsilon_{ijl} \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta l} \quad (2.35)$$

$$\Phi^+ = G_D \left[2h_R \mathcal{P}_R - 2h_L \mathcal{P}_L + e^{ia/f_a} h_R \zeta \mathcal{P}_L - e^{-ia/f_a} h_L \zeta \mathcal{P}_R \right] i\gamma_5 \varepsilon_{ijl} \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta l}. \quad (2.36)$$

In the above equations, the first two terms arise from the one-gluon exchange interaction, while those proportional to ζ arise from the one-instanton exchange. The matrix satisfies $\Phi^+ = \gamma_0 (\Phi^-)^\dagger \gamma_0$.

CFL

In Chapter 1, we examined the various phases of superconductive quark matter. Among these phases, we identified the Color-Flavor Locking (CFL) phase, in which the color and flavor of the quarks are locked together. Additionally, we recognized that the CFL phase may form at high densities. However, we also acknowledged that first-principle QCD, such as lattice QCD and pQCD, cannot be applied in this context. Consequently, we employed QCD-like effective models that can encapsulate the dense quark dynamics. The fundamental structure of the model is presented in Chapter 2. Building upon the framework established in the preceding section, this chapter will derive the thermodynamic potential, dispersion relations, gap equations, and analyze the axion potential, topological susceptibility.

3.1 Thermodynamic potential for CFL

The complete Lagrangian for our model is given by:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{V} + \bar{\Psi} S^{-1} \Psi, \quad (3.1)$$

where the inverse quark propagator is given by

$$S^{-1}(p) = \begin{pmatrix} (\not{p} + \mu\gamma_0)1_C 1_F & \Phi^- \\ \Phi^+ & (\not{p} - \mu\gamma_0)1_C 1_F \end{pmatrix}; \quad (3.2)$$

In this context, the symbols $\mathbf{1}_C$ and $\mathbf{1}_F$ correspond to the identities in color and flavor spaces, respectively. It should be noted that these matrices have a dimension of $4 \times 3 \times 3 \times 2 = 72$, due to the Dirac, color, flavor and Gorkov indices, respectively.

Thermodynamic potential is calculated by integrating over fermion fields in the partition function, resulting in

$$\Omega = -\mathcal{V} + \Omega_{1\text{-loop}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where \mathcal{V} denotes the mean field contribution (4.4), and $\Omega_{1\text{-loop}}$ corresponds to the 1-loop contribution of the quarks, namely

$$\Omega_{1\text{-loop}} = -T \sum_n \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{1}{2} \text{Tr} \log \left(\beta S^{-1}(i\omega_n, \vec{p}) \right). \quad (3.4)$$

In order to obtain Eq. (3.4), we performed a functional integral over fermions at a fixed value of a . In this work, the axion field is treated as a classical background, which implies that the thermodynamic potential is a function of a . Consequently, physical quantities must be computed at a given value of a . Furthermore, the imaginary time formalism of finite temperature field theory was employed, with the relevant fermionic Matsubara frequencies being given by $\omega_n = (2n + 1)\pi T$. The overall factor of $1/2$ in Eq. (3.4) accounts for the artificial doubling of degrees of freedom introduced by the transformation to the Nambu-Gorkov bi-spinors. Furthermore, the trace is to be interpreted in Dirac, colour and flavour space.

In order to evaluate the sum over ω_n in Eq. (3.4), one should get the eigenvalues of the inverse propagator S^{-1} . Since $\det \gamma_0 = 1$ we can write

$$\det S^{-1} = \det \gamma_0 S^{-1}, \quad (3.5)$$

hence, the eigenvalue problem for S^{-1} is equivalent to that of $\gamma_0 S^{-1}$. Then, writing

$$\gamma_0 S^{-1} = p_0 \mathbf{1}_{72 \times 72} + \mathcal{T}, \quad (3.6)$$

where matrix \mathcal{T} is

$$\mathcal{T} = \begin{pmatrix} (-\gamma_0 \vec{p} \cdot \vec{\gamma} + \mu) \mathbf{1}_C \mathbf{1}_F & \gamma_0 \Phi^- \\ \gamma_0 \Phi^+ & (-\gamma_0 \vec{p} \cdot \vec{\gamma} - \mu) \mathbf{1}_C \mathbf{1}_F \end{pmatrix}, \quad (3.7)$$

we note that the eigenvalue problem of S^{-1} is equivalent to that of the matrix \mathcal{T} . We obtain the eigenvalues of \mathcal{T}

$$\varepsilon_{1,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (3.8)$$

$$\varepsilon_{2,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (3.9)$$

$$\varepsilon_{3,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (3.10)$$

$$\varepsilon_{4,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\varepsilon_{5,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + \Delta_7^2}, \quad (3.12)$$

$$\varepsilon_{6,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + \Delta_7^2}, \quad (3.13)$$

$$\varepsilon_{7,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + \Delta_9^2}, \quad (3.14)$$

$$\varepsilon_{8,\pm} = \pm \sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + \Delta_9^2}, \quad (3.15)$$

The eigenvalues (3.8 - 3.15) indicate the presence of a gap, Δ , which suggests that all quarks are involved in the pairing process, representing the Color-Flavor Locking (CFL) phase. Here, p represents the magnitude $|p|$ of the three momentum vector \vec{p} , and μ is quark chemical potential. Each equation (3.8 - 3.11) has multiplicity of 8 ($8 \times 4 = 32$), while eigenvalues from (3.12 - 3.15) gives multiplicity of 1 ($1 \times 4 = 4$). This in total, considering the pairs of equations, makes up 72 eigenvalues which in essence was the dimension of the matrix (3.7) which we diagonalized. The squared gaps are taken as

$$\Delta_3^2 = \zeta^2 G_D^2 h_L^2 + 4G_D^2 h_R^2 - 4\zeta G_D^2 h_L h_R \cos(a/fa), \quad (3.16)$$

$$\Delta_5^2 = \zeta^2 G_D^2 h_R^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 - 4\zeta G_D^2 h_L h_R \cos(a/fa), \quad (3.17)$$

$$\Delta_7^2 = 4\Delta_3^2, \quad (3.18)$$

$$\Delta_9^2 = 4\Delta_5^2, \quad (3.19)$$

Our objective was to identify the total unique eigenvalues as a composition of the form: $8 \otimes 1$. The gap in the quark spectrum in the CFL phase can be better understood through Figure. (3.1). If we consider that $\Delta = 0$, then there is a node in the quark spectrum, indicating that for some non-zero momentum, we find a zero in the energy. The dispersion relations

with $\Delta = 0$ demonstrate the normal phase of quark matter. Conversely, a finite value of Δ results in the emergence of the superconducting phase.

Figure 3.1: Energy E MeV vs. Momentum p MeV for CFL phase. With quark chemical potential $\mu = 500$ MeV and Δ is taken to be 100 MeV.

Now, we can consider the positive eigenvalues as $\varepsilon_k(\vec{p}) = \varepsilon_{k,+}(\vec{p})$, $k = 1, \dots, 8$. We utilize the matrix exponential property; $\ln \det \beta S^{-1} = \text{Tr} \ln \beta S^{-1}$ and write down as sums multiplied by degeneracy.

$$\ln \det \beta S_L^{-1}(i\omega_n, \vec{p}) = 8 \sum_{k=1}^4 \ln \left(\frac{\omega_n^2 + \varepsilon_k(\vec{p})^2}{T^2} \right) + \sum_{k=5}^8 \ln \left(\frac{\omega_n^2 + \varepsilon_k(\vec{p})^2}{T^2} \right), \quad (3.20)$$

In order to arrive at an explicit expression for $\Omega_{1\text{-loop}}^L$ we are using the Matsubara sum [37] in the following manner

$$T \sum_n \ln \left(\frac{\omega_n^2 + \varepsilon_k(\vec{p})^2}{T^2} \right) = |\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})| + 2T \ln \left(1 + e^{-|\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})|/T} \right), \quad (3.21)$$

Now after using the equation (3.21) in the (3.4) with appropriate degeneracy discussed earlier, we finally get the 1-loop contribution to the dynamics

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega_{1\text{-loop}}^L &= -4 \sum_{k=1}^4 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[\varepsilon_k(\vec{p}) + 2T \ln \left(1 + e^{-\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})/T} \right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=5}^8 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[\varepsilon_k(\vec{p}) + 2T \ln \left(1 + e^{-\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})/T} \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (3.22)$$

where energies $|\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})|$ is considered to have only positive solution. Using expression of $\Omega_{1\text{-loop}}^L$ and mean-field contribution (4.4), we can write thermodynamic potential

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &= 2G_D(h_R^2 + h_L^2) - 2\zeta G_D h_L h_R \cos\left(\frac{a}{f_a}\right) \\ &\quad - 8 \times \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^4 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[\varepsilon_k(\vec{p}) + 2T \ln \left(1 + e^{-\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})/T} \right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=5}^8 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[\varepsilon_k(\vec{p}) + 2T \ln \left(1 + e^{-\varepsilon_k(\vec{p})/T} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.23)$$

It is crucial to acknowledge that NJL models are non-renormalizable. The divergences inherent to these models are typically addressed through the implementation of distinct regularization techniques. In the context of thermal field theory, integrals are regularized by employing either a sharp or a smooth three-momentum cutoff. This approach effectively preserves the analytical structure of the model. In equation (3.22), we face the similar issue of having divergence in ultraviolet region when $T = 0$. This divergence is removed by sharp 3-momentum cutoff (Λ) regularization, and the first term can rewritten as

$$\int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \varepsilon_k(p) = \frac{4\pi}{8\pi^3} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \varepsilon_k(p). \quad (3.24)$$

The equation (3.24) is commonly adapted in the simplest versions of the QED superconductivity. In QED superconductivity, lattice is present to complement the weakly attractive interaction. However, there is no lattice in QCD. Therefore, In our analysis, we treat the parameter Λ as a free

variable of the model and, drawing upon previous studies based on the NJL model, we posit $\Lambda = O(1\text{GeV})$. The aforementioned cutoff approximately represents the momentum scale above which it would be replaced by the contact interaction employed within the present work with a non-local term directly derived from QCD.

3.2 θ -dependence of the gap

It is quite evident from the equations of the gap that if $\zeta = 0$ then gap parameter Δ^2 and consequently thermodynamic potential are only dependent on h_L^2 or h_R^2 . As long as $\zeta = 0$ (up panel) and $T = 0$, there are four degenerate minima along the lines $h_L = \pm h_R$ which can be seen in figure (3.2) to be removed as the coupling ζ turns on (down panel). The x -axis represents the Δ_L and y -axis is plotted for Δ_R , both in MeV. The definitions of the Δ_L and Δ_R are given as

$$\Delta_L = 2G_D h_L \quad , \quad \Delta_R = 2G_D h_R. \quad (3.25)$$

The definitions provided in Eq. (3.25) facilitate the distinction between pseudoscalar and scalar condensate.

$$\Delta_{\text{PS}} = \Delta_R + \Delta_L, \quad \Delta_{\text{S}} = \Delta_R - \Delta_L. \quad (3.26)$$

As illustrated in Fig. (3.2, when the parameter ζ is set to zero, two degenerate minima emerge. One of these represents the pseudo scalar condensate, with $\Delta_L = \Delta_R$, while the other depicts the scalar condensate, with $\Delta_L = -\Delta_R$. In presence of the one-gluon-exchange only, the condensation energy in the scalar and the pseudoscalar channels are the same. Conversely, when the value of ζ is set to 0.2, it is observed that one of the loci is removed, resulting in a state that corresponds to the scalar condensate. This state is physically related to instanton-induced interactions.

Figure 3.2: The thermodynamic potential at $T = 0$ was calculated for two cases: $\theta \equiv a/f_a = 0$ and $\zeta = 0$ (up panel) and for $\zeta = 0.2$ (down panel). The plots show that the x and y axes represent Δ_L and Δ_R respectively which are measured in MeV.

It is worth noting that Figure (3.3 - 3.5) has been plotted at $\zeta = 0.2$ and $T = 0$ for a range of values of θ , with the coupling $G_D = 2.9$ GeV held constant. The resulting plots provide evidence for the invariant transformations between $\Delta_L = \pm\Delta_R$. As the global minimum of Ω is on the lines $h_L = \pm h_R$, there are transitions from scalar condensate to pseudoscalar condensate. For instance, from $\theta \in [0, \pi/2)$, we have scalar condensate. However, for values of theta in the interval $[\pi/2, 3\pi/2]$, the condensate changes from scalar to pseudoscalar, resulting in a minimum at $\Delta_L = \Delta_R$. If the a/f_a is increased further, the number of loci is reduced, and a transition to the scalar condensate is observed with a value of $\theta = 2\pi$, which is the same as the top-left panel evaluated at $\theta = 0$. Furthermore, it is crucial to emphasise that negative values of ζ merely invert the role of the pseudoscalar and scalar condensates. Therefore, these values do not impact the analytical process.

Figure 3.3: Thermodynamic potential at $T = 0$, computed for $a_1 = a_2 = 1$, $\zeta = 0.2$, $G_D = 2.9$ and several values of $\theta \equiv a/f_a$. In the plot, x and y -axes denote Δ_L and Δ_R respectively (measured in MeV). Left plot corresponds to $\theta = 0$, and right to $\theta = \pi/2 - \epsilon$. Where the value of $\epsilon = 0.1$.

Figure 3.4: Same parameters as the Fig (3.3). Left plot corresponds to $\theta = \pi/2$, and right to $\theta = \pi/2 + \epsilon$. Here $\epsilon = 0.1$.

Figure 3.5: Same parameters as the Fig (3.3). Left plots corresponds to $\theta = \pi$, and finally right to $\theta = 2\pi$.

3.3 HDET Gap Equation at zero temperature for CFL phase

In order to get non-trivial solution for the gap equation for allowed values of ζ , we will be evaluating the gap equation at $T = 0$ and small θ . In this realm, the equation (3.23) can be minimized in the direction of h_L by taking $\partial\Omega/\partial h_L = 0$, and taking the limit $h_L = -h_R$, we yield the following result

$$2 + \zeta \cos(a/f_a) = \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{A(a, \zeta)}{\sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{A(a, \zeta)}{\sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \mu \rightarrow -\mu \right), \quad (3.27)$$

where $A(a, \zeta)$ is defined as

$$A(a, \zeta) = 4 + 4\zeta \cos(a/f_a) + \zeta^2. \quad (3.28)$$

It can be observed from Eq. (3.27) that the right-hand side is always positive. However, in order to satisfy the left-hand side for any value of a , the non-trivial solution can only be obtained if $|\zeta| < 2$. Therefore, we will only be considering $\zeta < 2$ in our calculations. We can also approximate to better understand the relationship of h_L with a . For this purpose, we divide both sides of the Eq. (3.27) with $(2 + \zeta \cos a/f_a)$, and considering the function

$$\Theta(a, \zeta) = \frac{A(a, \zeta)}{2 + \zeta \cos(a/f_a)}. \quad (3.29)$$

And we obtain

$$1 = \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \Theta(a, \zeta) \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{(p - \mu)^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{(p + \mu)^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right), \quad (3.30)$$

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The integral may be calculated by applying High Density Effective Theory (HDET). As a consequence of asymptotic freedom in QCD (large p), at large chemical potentials μ , the sole relevant degrees of freedom are the interactions near the Fermi surface. Consequently, in equation (3.30), the integrals with $p - \mu$ are likely to receive considerable contributions at high μ . Conversely, the integrals with $p - \mu$ at large μ will not be significant at $p \approx \mu$. Therefore, integrals containing $p - \mu$ terms can be disregarded, and we can introduce the thin shell around $p = \mu$ in which δ can be taken as the width of the shell. Furthermore, we can substitute $\zeta = p - \mu$, which yields the following equation.

$$1 = \frac{G_D \mu^2}{\pi^2} \Theta(a, \zeta) \int_{-\delta}^{+\delta} \left(\frac{d\zeta}{\sqrt{\zeta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{d\zeta}{2\sqrt{\zeta^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right). \quad (3.31)$$

By applying weak coupling limit $\delta \gg G_D h_L$, we can obtain exact solution of the integrals.

$$1 = \frac{G_D \mu^2}{\pi^2} \Theta(a, \zeta) \log \left(1 + \frac{2\delta^2 + 2\sqrt{\delta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}}{G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)} \right) + \frac{G_D \mu^2}{2\pi^2} \Theta(a, \zeta) \log \left(1 + \frac{2\delta^2 + 2\sqrt{\delta^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}}{4G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)} \right). \quad (3.32)$$

And by using Eq. (3.25), we obtain

$$\Delta_L = \frac{\sqrt{8}\delta}{\sqrt{A(a, \zeta)}} \exp \left(-\frac{\pi^2}{4\mu^2 G_D \Theta(a, \zeta)} \right). \quad (3.33)$$

The High Density Effective Theory (HDET) solution of QCD obtained in (3.33) has parallels with the gap in the BCS theory of superconductivity. The solution have validity in the weak-coupling limit, in which $\delta \gg G_D h_L$. Here, μ^2 is proportional to the density of the states of the quarks pairs close to the Fermi shell, and δ can be considered similar to the Debye frequency ω as in the conventional superconductivity.

Figure 3.6: The gap Δ_L at $T = 0$ and $\mu = 400$ MeV is plotted against a/f_a for several values of ζ . In order to have $\Delta_L = 50$ MeV, G_D is fixed.

Figure 3.7: The gap Δ_L at $T = 0$ and $\mu = 400$ MeV is plotted against a/f_a for several values of ζ . In order to have $\Delta_R = 50$ MeV, G_D is fixed.

3.4 Axion Potential

We have computed the axion potential and plotted against $\theta = a/f_a$ at $T = 0$ and $\mu = 400$ MeV in the Fig. (3.8). Here, axion potential is defined as

$$V(\theta) \equiv \Omega(\theta) - \Omega(0), \quad (3.34)$$

We can observe the periodicity in the axion potential which is in agreement with the calculations posed in Figures (3.6) and (3.7). The periodic behavior in axion potential in the presence of superconductive phase is happening at the sequence of every π rotations. In comparison to the axions in presence of chiral and η condensate, where axion potential repeats itself with 2π . In this context, it gives rise to the domain walls.

Figure 3.8: At $T = 0$, $\mu = 400$ MeV, and $\Lambda = 1000$ MeV, the axion potential $V(a/f_a) = \Omega(a/f_a) - \Omega(0)$ is plotted against the a/f_a for several values. G_D is fixed for having fixed gap $\Delta_L = 50$ MeV.

3.5 Topological Susceptibility

In the context of our model, topological susceptibility which gives the measure of the topological charge can be obtained as

$$\chi = \left. \frac{d^2\Omega}{d\theta^2} \right|_{\theta=0}, \quad (3.35)$$

where $\theta = a/f_a$. Using Eq. (3.27) in Eq. (3.35), the topological susceptibility is realized as

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= 2\zeta G_D h_L h_R - \frac{2}{\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} (\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_3 + \mu \rightarrow -\mu) \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \theta^2} (\varepsilon_5 + \varepsilon_7 + \mu \rightarrow -\mu). \end{aligned} \quad (3.36)$$

Here, we can also use the transformation $h_L = -h_R$ as it is relevant for small angle θ in Eq. (3.36).

$$\begin{aligned} \chi &= 8\zeta G_D h_L^2 \left[-\frac{1}{4} + \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(p-\mu)^2 + (2+\zeta)^2 G_D^2 h_L^2}} + \mu \rightarrow -\mu \right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{G_D}{2\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(p-\mu)^2 + 4(2+\zeta)^2 G_D^2 h_L^2}} + \mu \rightarrow -\mu \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.37)$$

Moreover, the gap equation which we obtained in Eq. (3.27) at $\theta = 0$ is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2+\zeta} &= \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{(p-\mu)^2 + (2+\zeta)^2 G_D^2 h_L^2}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{(p-\mu)^2 + 4(2+\zeta)^2 G_D^2 h_L^2}} + \mu \rightarrow -\mu \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.38)$$

Using Eq. (3.38) in (3.37), we finally obtain the complete expression for the topological susceptibility

$$\chi = 2\zeta G_D h_L^2 \left(\frac{2 - \zeta}{2 + \zeta} \right). \quad (3.39)$$

Eventually, taking into account $\Delta_L = 2G_D h_L$, we can rewrite topological susceptibility as

$$\chi = \frac{\Delta_L^2}{2G_D} \zeta \frac{2 - \zeta}{2 + \zeta}. \quad (3.40)$$

Figure 3.9: At $T = 0$, $\mu = 400$ MeV, and $\Lambda = 1000$ MeV, the topological susceptibility χ^4 is plotted against the ζ for several fixed values of gap Δ_L . G_D remains fixed to obtain the value of fixed gap $\Delta_L = 25, 50, 100$ MeV.

The form of topological susceptibility obtained in Eq. (3.40) is done at $a/f_a = 0$. The expression stands correct at both $T = 0$ and finite

temperature limit as momentum integrals in Eq. (3.38) are changed in the same way at $T \neq 0$. We have already discussed the role of ζ that if $\zeta < 0$ is considered, there is inversion between pseudo-scalar and scalar condensate. For the minima which is formed on the line $h_L = h_R$, we get

$$\chi = -\frac{\Delta_L^2}{2G_D} \zeta \frac{2 + \zeta}{2 - \zeta}. \quad (3.41)$$

In essence, the complete topological susceptibility encapsulating different lines such as $h_L = -h_R$ and $h_L = h_R$

$$\chi = \frac{\Delta_L^2}{2G_D} |\zeta| \frac{2 - |\zeta|}{2 + |\zeta|}. \quad (3.42)$$

Figure 3.10: The topological susceptibility χ plotted analytically from the formula given in Eq. (3.40) with $G_D \Lambda^2 = 1.575$ for $\Delta_L = 50$ MeV with numerical evaluation.

A numerical estimate of topological susceptibility was conducted in Lattice QCD, χ PT, and NJL models, yielding a value of approximately 78 MeV at $T = 0$ and $\mu = 0$ [27]. Finally, we have plotted the $\chi^{1/4}$ for ζ in range of values of $[0, 2)$ in Fig. (3.9) by fixed G_D to have $\Delta_L = 25, 50, 100$.

3.6 Axion Mass and Self-Coupling

The low-energy Lagrangian density in the context of axion fields can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}_a = \frac{1}{2} \partial^\mu a \partial_\mu a - \frac{m_a^2}{2} a^2 - \frac{\lambda_a}{4!} a^4, \quad (3.43)$$

where the axions mass m_a and self-coupling given by quartic term λ_a^4 are given in terms of the thermodynamic potential Ω

$$m_a^2 = \frac{1}{f_a^2} \left. \frac{d^2 \Omega}{d\theta^2} \right|_{\theta=0}, \quad \lambda_a = \frac{1}{f_a^4} \left. \frac{d^4 V(\theta)}{d\theta^4} \right|_{\theta=0}, \quad (3.44)$$

We can notice that topological susceptibility is related to the axion mass squared term with a factor of $1/f_a^2$. Therefore, as we have already found the expression for topological susceptibility, axion mass term is pretty straightforward. By using Eq. (3.42), we can write

$$m_a^2 = \frac{\Delta_L^2}{2G_D f_a^2} |\zeta| \frac{2 - |\zeta|}{2 + |\zeta|}. \quad (3.45)$$

However, we were unable to find the analytical result for the self-coupling. Therefore, we resorted to numerical calculations. In Fig. 3.11, we found quartic self-coupling term for different values of ζ under the limit that ζ only has non-trivial solutions when $\zeta < 2$. The calculation has been done for fixing the Δ_L at 25, 50 and 100 MeV.

Figure 3.11: Axions self coupling, $\lambda_a f_a^4$, plotted against ζ for several fixed values of gap $\Delta_L = 25, 50, 100$ MeV.

We observe that self-coupling have negative values at smaller values of ζ and changes sign depending on the Δ_L . It is found in NJL studies that $\lambda_a f_a^4 = -(55.64 \text{ MeV})^4$ at $T = 0$ and $\mu = 0$. The negative values of the quartic interaction signifies that it is attractive. Similarly, as we also found positive values at larger ζ , the quartic interaction becomes negative and consequently repulsive.

Chapter 4

2SC

We briefly discussed the pure 2SC phase in which both quarks (up and down) participating in the BCS-like pairing were massless. In this case, the gauge symmetry group was broken down to the subgroup $SU(2)_c$ by Higgs mechanism and five of the gluons obtained Meissner mass. This is the relevant phase in QCD phase diagram at intermediate densities e.g. strange mass can be ignored. However, we introduce the quark mass by shifting the chemical potential by $m^2/2\mu$ which is one of the choices that can be justified through the charge neutrality n_Q conditions. It is important to note that matter inside the compact stars should be neutral (effectively $n_q = 0$) on average otherwise it will not be bound by the gravity as it is weaker than the electromagnetic force. In the particular case of the two-flavor quark matter, neutrality condition can be imposed by having number density n_d of the down quark as to be twice the number density n_u of the up quark; $n_d \approx 2n_u$. We can also realize this by writing the di-quark chemical potential

$$\hat{\mu} = \begin{pmatrix} \mu - \frac{2}{3}\mu_e & 0 \\ 0 & \mu + \frac{1}{3}\mu_e \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbf{1}_c, \quad (4.1)$$

where μ_e is the electric chemical potential. If μ_e is non-zero, then there exists difference in the chemical potential of the up and down quark as $\delta\mu = \mu_e/2$. Therefore, chemical potential needs to be adjusted to balance the contributions of different quark flavors and electrons. Similarly, if we consider example of pairing of up and strange quark, the large strange

quark mass will significantly shift the chemical potential. In order to achieve electrical neutrality and taking different quark masses into account, we relax the approximation of the quarks with the same chemical potential.

4.1 2SC model with one massive quark

In this section, we consider a modified 2SC model in which one of the two quarks has a finite mass. The impact of the mass is incorporated at the leading order by shifting the chemical potential by the quantity $\delta\mu = m^2/2\mu$. Consequently, the quark chemical potential matrix is expressed in color-flavor space as

$$\begin{pmatrix} \mu_u & 0 \\ 0 & \mu_d \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbb{1}_C = \begin{pmatrix} \mu & 0 \\ 0 & \mu - \delta\mu \end{pmatrix} \otimes \mathbb{1}_C. \quad (4.2)$$

Rewriting the interaction lagrangian density which we introduced in the chapter 2

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{int}} = \mathcal{V} + \bar{\Psi}\Delta\Psi, \quad (4.3)$$

where

$$\mathcal{V} = -2G_D(h_R^2 + h_L^2) + 2\zeta G_D h_L h_R \cos\left(\frac{a}{f_a}\right), \quad (4.4)$$

and

$$\Delta = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & \Phi^- \\ \Phi^+ & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad (4.5)$$

with

$$\Phi^- = G_D \left[2h_R \mathcal{P}_L - 2h_L \mathcal{P}_R - e^{ia/f_a} h_L \zeta \mathcal{P}_L + e^{-ia/f_a} h_R \zeta \mathcal{P}_R \right] i\gamma_5 \varepsilon_{ij3} \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta 3} \quad (4.6)$$

$$\Phi^+ = G_D \left[2h_R \mathcal{P}_R - 2h_L \mathcal{P}_L + e^{ia/f_a} h_R \zeta \mathcal{P}_L - e^{-ia/f_a} h_L \zeta \mathcal{P}_R \right] i\gamma_5 \varepsilon_{ij3} \varepsilon_{\alpha\beta 3}. \quad (4.7)$$

In the Eqs. (4.6 - 4.7), Levi-Civita symbol which represents the anti-symmetric tensor in flavor and color space respectively and ensure the

Pauli exclusion principle is summed over up and down quarks with red and green colors. It is different from the CFL case where all three quarks (up, down, and strange) were considered. In this case the quark condensate points in the direction of the blue quark which also means that the up and down blue quarks do not participate in the pairing.

The eigenvalues obtained by following a similar formalism as outlined in the previous chapter are as follows

$$\varepsilon_1 = -p - \mu, \quad (4.8)$$

$$\varepsilon_2 = p - \mu, \quad (4.9)$$

$$\varepsilon_3 = -p + \mu, \quad (4.10)$$

$$\varepsilon_4 = p + \mu, \quad (4.11)$$

$$\varepsilon_5 = -p + \delta\mu - \mu, \quad (4.12)$$

$$\varepsilon_6 = p + \delta\mu - \mu, \quad (4.13)$$

$$\varepsilon_7 = -p - \delta\mu + \mu, \quad (4.14)$$

$$\varepsilon_8 = p - \delta\mu + \mu, \quad (4.15)$$

$$\varepsilon_9 = -\frac{\delta\mu}{2} - \sqrt{(p - \mu + \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (4.16)$$

$$\varepsilon_{10} = -\frac{\delta\mu}{2} - \sqrt{(p + \mu - \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (4.17)$$

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \frac{\delta\mu}{2} + \sqrt{(p - \mu + \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (4.18)$$

$$\varepsilon_{12} = \frac{\delta\mu}{2} + \sqrt{(p + \mu - \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (4.19)$$

$$\varepsilon_{13} = -\frac{\delta\mu}{2} + \sqrt{(p - \mu + \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (4.20)$$

$$\varepsilon_{14} = -\frac{\delta\mu}{2} + \sqrt{(p + \mu - \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_3^2}, \quad (4.21)$$

$$\varepsilon_{15} = \frac{\delta\mu}{2} - \sqrt{(p - \mu + \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (4.22)$$

$$\varepsilon_{16} = \frac{\delta\mu}{2} - \sqrt{(p + \mu - \delta\mu)^2 + \Delta_5^2}, \quad (4.23)$$

Each dispersion law for unpaired quarks has multiplicity of two, while eigenvalues of paired quarks have multiplicity of four. The unpaired

quarks are the blue quarks which do not participate in the pairing. Moreover we have

$$\Delta_3^2 = \zeta^2 G_D^2 h_L^2 + 4G_D^2 h_R^2 - 4\zeta G_D^2 h_L h_R \cos(a/fa), \quad (4.24)$$

$$\Delta_5^2 = \zeta^2 G_D^2 h_R^2 + 4G_D^2 h_L^2 - 4\zeta G_D^2 h_L h_R \cos(a/fa), \quad (4.25)$$

These results are in agreement with the massless 2SC phase for $\delta\mu = 0$. We can write the thermodynamics potential considering potential \mathcal{V} and $\Omega_{1\text{-loop}}$ in the spirit of previous calculations.

$$\begin{aligned} \Omega &= 2G_D(h_R^2 + h_L^2) - 2\zeta G_D h_L h_R \cos\left(\frac{a}{f_a}\right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{k=1}^8 \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[|\epsilon_k(\vec{p})| + 2T \ln\left(1 + e^{-|\epsilon_k(\vec{p})|/T}\right) \right] \\ &\quad - 2 \sum_{k=9}^{16} \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} \left[|\epsilon(\vec{p})| + 2T \ln\left(1 + e^{-|\epsilon(\vec{p})|/T}\right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4.26)$$

The sum over the first eight eigenvalues (4.8-4.15) runs over the unpaired quarks, hence it does not contribute to the quark condensate, while the contribution of the paired quarks corresponds to the last summation. In last term, we observe that eigenvalues from (4.20-4.23), taking absolute value enforces solution with separate limit in which $\delta\mu \gg \Delta$. At first, We are simplifying the notation by this notation

$$\alpha = p + \mu - \frac{\delta\mu}{2}, \quad (4.27)$$

$$\beta = p - \mu + \frac{\delta\mu}{2}. \quad (4.28)$$

Therefore, we will evaluate the last term with explicit integration limits for (4.20-4.23) in the following manner

$$\begin{aligned} -2 \sum_{k=9}^{16} \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} |\epsilon(\vec{p})| &= -2 \left(\frac{4\pi}{8\pi^3} \right) \int p^2 dp [|\epsilon_9| + |\epsilon_{10}| + |\epsilon_{11}| + |\epsilon_{12}| \\ &\quad + |\epsilon_{13}| + |\epsilon_{14}| + |\epsilon_{15}| + |\epsilon_{16}|], \end{aligned} \quad (4.29)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{1}{\pi^2} \left[\int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp (\epsilon_9 + \epsilon_{10} + \epsilon_{11} + \epsilon_{12}) + \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right) \right. \\
&\quad + \left(\int_0^{\mu^-} p^2 dp + \int_{\mu^+}^\Lambda p^2 dp \right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu + \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\int_0^{\mu^-} p^2 dp + \int_{\mu^+}^\Lambda p^2 dp \right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu + \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \left(\int_0^{\mu^-} p^2 dp + \int_{\mu^+}^\Lambda p^2 dp \right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu + \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) \\
&\quad + \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) \\
&\quad \left. + \left(\int_0^{\mu^-} p^2 dp + \int_{\mu^+}^\Lambda p^2 dp \right) \left(-\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu + \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) \right], \tag{4.30}
\end{aligned}$$

Adding and subtracting the terms like $\int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{(p + \mu - \delta\mu/2)^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right)$
 $+ \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{(p - \mu + \delta\mu/2)^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right)$ for each integral.

$$\begin{aligned}
-2 \sum_{k=9}^{16} \int \frac{d^3 p}{(2\pi)^3} |\epsilon(\vec{p})| &= -\frac{1}{\pi^2} \left[2 \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_3^2} + \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_3^2} + \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) + 2 \int_{\mu^-}^{\mu^+} p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_3^2} + \frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_3^2} \right. \right. \\
&\quad \left. \left. + \frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\alpha^2 + \Delta_5^2} + \frac{1}{2} \delta\mu - \sqrt{\beta^2 + \Delta_5^2} \right) \right], \tag{4.31}
\end{aligned}$$

Now, after getting the final form of (4.26), the gap equation can be studied by applying stationary condition in terms of h_L (taking $\partial\Omega/\partial h_L$) and

using the fact $h_L = -h_R$

$$2 + \zeta \cos(a/f_a) = \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp A(a, \zeta) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) - \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} \int_{-\mu}^\mu p^2 dp A(a, \zeta) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right), \quad (4.32)$$

where $A(a, \zeta)$ is given by Eq. (3.28). The non-trivial solution for the ζ exists when $\zeta < 2$.

4.2 Topological Susceptibility

Topological susceptibility can be found by the definition mentioned in (3.35) and treating under the same formalism in which $h_L = -h_R$ with small angle approximation, we get

$$\chi = -2\zeta G_D h_L^2 + \frac{8G_D^2 h_L^2 \zeta}{\pi^2} \left[\int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp A(a, \zeta) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) - \int_{-\mu}^\mu p^2 dp A(a, \zeta) \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) \right], \quad (4.33)$$

Evaluating the gap equation for massive 2SC (4.32) at $\theta = a/f_a = 0$,

$$2 + \zeta = \frac{G_D(2 + \zeta)^2}{\pi^2} \left[\int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) - \int_{-\mu}^\mu p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) \right], \quad (4.34)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{(2+\zeta)} = \frac{G_D}{\pi^2} & \left[\int_0^\Lambda p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) \right. \\ & \left. - \int_{-\mu}^\mu p^2 dp \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} + \frac{1}{\sqrt{\beta^2 + G_D^2 h_L^2 A(a, \zeta)}} \right) \right], \end{aligned} \quad (4.35)$$

Finally, after utilizing the (4.35), we arrive at the expression of topological susceptibility

$$\chi = 2\zeta G_D h_L^2 \left(\frac{2-\zeta}{2+\zeta} \right). \quad (4.36)$$

We observe that we found the same analytical expression for the topological susceptibility in the both case of CFL phase and 2SC phase.

Conclusion and Prospects

This is the first time that the coupling of axions to a three-flavour color superconductor (CFL) phase has been studied within a microscopic model inspired from the Nambu-Jona Lasino like models. This allows us to take into account both condensation in scalar $\Delta_R - \Delta_L$ and pseudo-scalar $\Delta_R + \Delta_L$ channels. The model is based on interaction which contains two terms: one of the term is $U(1)_A$ preserving, and the other is $U(1)_A$ breaking term. The $U(1)_A$ preserving term having the coupling strength G_D is considered to be originated from the one gluon exchange. On the other hand, $U(1)_A$ violating term have the coupling strength of the form ζG . In essence, the $U(1)_A$ breaking term takes into account the coupling of the axions to the quarks. Furthermore, the eigenvalues of the CFL system has been obtained, all of them are gapped and contain the multiplicity of $8 + 1$ as expected from this phase. The thermodynamic potential is calculated and plotted for the cases in which axion field is inactive $\theta = 0$ and also the response of system when it turns on. In these calculations, G_D is taken to be free parameter with ζ in the range of $[0, 2)$ due to non-triviality of ζ in this range. The negative values of the ζ just exchange the role of psuedo-scalar and scalar condensate.

This is also the first time that the axion potential θ in a CFL phase of dense quark matter has been computed. Moreover, the complete analytical formula for the topological susceptibility, χ in a Color-Flavor Locking

(CFL) phase has been determined, and the result is in agreement with the previous findings in a Two-Flavour Color superconductor (2SC) phase. In addition, the axion mass, m_a , which is related to the topological susceptibility, $\chi_a = m_a^2 f_a^2$, and axion self-coupling λ_a were computed in the CFL phase. We found that a range of ζ for which λ_a becomes positive which is unique result as compared to the calculations done for the normal quark matter.

In a similar vein, we have conducted calculations for the 2SC phase with one quark being massive. The quark mass was required because strong interactions make quarks heavier than their bare mass. Therefore, it is not a good approximation to ignore the quark mass. The introduction of one massive quark was to ascertain how the picture of the 2SC phase changes. The mass was introduced by shifting the chemical potential. The thermodynamic potential was obtained in this phase as well. However, by setting $\mu = 0$, we can obtain results for the pure 2SC phase, in which both quarks are massless. The primary objective in considering the 2SC system with one massive quark is to determine the topological susceptibility. Consequently, we obtained the same expression for the topological susceptibility as that found in the CFL phase or pure 2SC phase. Based on the aforementioned analysis, it is possible to extend this study by including the actual mass of the quark and examining its effects. Analogous to the examination of 2SC with a single massive quark, it is possible to investigate the emergence of instability phenomena when $\delta\mu$ is considerably large and to determine the circumstances under which these instabilities may be removed. The study of superconductive phases with axions may also be relevant for astrophysical scales; specifically, in the interiors of compact stars, where axions could potentially become trapped and buried inside the core, and could couple with color superconductive phases.

Bibliography

- [1] David J. Gross and Frank Wilczek, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **30**, 1343 (1973).
- [2] D. Boyanovsky, H.J. de Vega, and D.J. Schwarz, *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science* **56**, 441–500 (2006).
- [3] Michael Creutz, *Quarks, Gluons and Lattices, Cambridge Monographs on Mathematical Physics* (Cambridge University Press, ADDRESS, 2023).
- [4] Eemeli Annala, Tyler Gorda, Aleksi Kurkela, Joonas Nättilä, and Aleksi Vuorinen, *Nature Physics* **16**, 907 (2020).
- [5] Mark G. Alford, Andreas Schmitt, Krishna Rajagopal, and Thomas Schäfer, *Reviews of Modern Physics* **80**, 1455–1515 (2008).
- [6] KRISHNA RAJAGOPAL and FRANK WILCZEK, in *At The Frontier of Particle Physics* (WORLD SCIENTIFIC, ADDRESS, 2001), p. 2061–2151.
- [7] KAMERLINGH ONNES H., *Comm. Phys. Lab. Univ. Leiden* **122**, 122 (1911).
- [8] James F Annett, *Superconductivity, Superfluids, and Condensates* (Oxford University Press, ADDRESS, 2004).
- [9] J. R. Schrieffer and M. Tinkham, *Rev. Mod. Phys.* **71**, S313 (1999).
- [10] J. Bardeen, L. N. Cooper, and J. R. Schrieffer, *Phys. Rev.* **108**, 1175 (1957).

- [11] V A Miransky, *Dynamical Symmetry Breaking in Quantum Field Theories* (WORLD SCIENTIFIC, ADDRESS, 1994).
- [12] Thomas Schäfer and Edward V. Shuryak, *Lect. Notes Phys.* **578**, 203 (2001).
- [13] Igor A. Shovkovy, *Foundations of Physics* **35**, 1309–1358 (2005).
- [14] D. Bailin and A. Love, **107**, 325 (1984).
- [15] Dirk H. Rischke, *International Journal of Modern Physics A* **16**, 1268 (2001).
- [16] Mark Alford, *Annual Review of Nuclear and Particle Science* **51**, 131–160 (2001).
- [17] Ta-Pei [0000-0002-1137-0969] Cheng and Ling-Fong [0000-0002-8035-3329] Li, *Gauge Theory of Elementary Particle Physics* (Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK, 1984).
- [18] Michael Creutz, *Annals of Physics* **324**, 1573–1584 (2009).
- [19] G. 't Hooft, *Phys. Rev. D* **14**, 3432 (1976).
- [20] C. Abel and Et al., *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **124**, 081803 (2020).
- [21] Dan-di Wu, *Z. Naturforsch. A* **52**, 179 (1997).
- [22] R. D. Peccei and Helen R. Quinn, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **38**, 1440 (1977).
- [23] R. D. Peccei and Helen R. Quinn, *Phys. Rev. D* **16**, 1791 (1977).
- [24] F. Wilczek, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **40**, 279 (1978).
- [25] Steven Weinberg, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **40**, 223 (1978).
- [26] Luca Di Luzio, Maurizio Giannotti, Enrico Nardi, and Luca Visinelli, *Physics Reports* **870**, 1 (2020), the landscape of QCD axion models.
- [27] Giovanni Grilli di Cortona, Edward Hardy, Javier Pardo Vega, and Giovanni Villadoro, *Journal of High Energy Physics* **2016**, (2016).

- [28] Georg G. Raffelt, in *Axions* (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, ADDRESS, YEAR), p. 51–71.
- [29] Ciaran O’Hare, cajohare/AxionLimits: AxionLimits, <https://cajohare.github.io/AxionLimits/>, 2020.
- [30] F. Weber, *Progress in Particle and Nuclear Physics* **54**, 193 (2005).
- [31] Keitaro Nagata, Shinji Motoki, Yoshiyuki Nakagawa, Atsushi Nakamura, Takuya Saito, and (XQCD-J Collaboration), *Progress of Theoretical and Experimental Physics* **2012**, 01A103 (2012).
- [32] Philippe de Forcrand, *Simulating QCD at finite density*, 2010.
- [33] M BUBALLA, *Physics Reports* **407**, 205–376 (2005).
- [34] Y. Nambu and G. Jona-Lasinio, *Phys. Rev.* **124**, 246 (1961).
- [35] Michael E. Peskin and Daniel V. Schroeder, *An Introduction to quantum field theory* (Addison-Wesley, Reading, USA, 1995).
- [36] Fabrizio Murgana, David E. Alvarez Castillo, Ana G. Grunfeld, and Marco Ruggieri, *Topological susceptibility and axion potential in two-flavor superconductive quark matter*, 2024.
- [37] Joseph I. Kapusta and Charles Gale, *Finite-Temperature Field Theory: Principles and Applications*, *Cambridge Monographs on Mathematical Physics*, 2 ed. (Cambridge University Press, ADDRESS, 2006).

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